

Basic Principles: The traits of hegemonic masculinity in *Hitch* (2005).

Abstract:

Hitch (2005) is a romantic comedy blockbuster that seemingly disrupts the self-evident truths about men and their relationship with the world. In this research, content analysis shows how the men closer to the ideals of hegemonic masculinity successfully employ physical force to control others, while they themselves are unable to constrain their aggressiveness, which is seen as manly and desirable. These men also agree with the dynamics of familial patriarchy, the values of the frontiersman and are always avoiding responsibility by stating that “Men will always be men”. Nevertheless, these men have to sacrifice their occupational success, resort to the make over and bend the laws of heterosexuality, to appear as more complete and alluring to women.

Introduction

In 2005, *Hitch* appeared in Hollywood's landscape as a film conscious of its own genre and tailored to appeal to a heterosexual male audience. Today, 17 years later, *Hitch* (2005) ranks as the third most successful blockbuster in the history of the romantic comedy genre, grossing more than 360 million dollars in theatre revenues only.

These financial figures show *Hitch's* importance as a movie able to reach a massive audience and now behaving as a force exceeding the theatre's space to be a phenomenon with the capacity to impact cultural perceptions of masculinity, gender values, romance, and normality through its reruns on different media platforms.

And while there is a growing literature on the many ways films impact the perception of masculinity in the audience, research of how certain expressions of masculinity become hegemonic in the rom-com blockbuster seems lacking as researchers cannot keep up with the constant inflow of films produced every year in said genre.

This paper aims to identify, through content analysis, the traits of hegemonic masculinity in *Hitch* (2005), a film about men's romantic anxieties and dreams in a genre usually centered around women.

Literature Review

Gramsci identified hegemony as the strategy by which a group ascends and maintains a position of power in a given society through the popularization of cultural ideals, which are presented as desirable and self-evident truths (Donaldson 1993). In this sense, hegemonic masculinity speaks of the ways in which a group of men comes to a position of power by presenting their vision of the world as a matter of common sense.

Nevertheless, this ideal masculinity is not a set of rigid characteristics, but a dynamic social construct whose permanent movement makes it somewhat unattainable to those who wish to embody it and difficult to pinpoint from a researcher's point of view (Connell, 1987. Mackinnon, 2003)

Hence, in this paper the analysis of hegemonic masculinity is performed on those men who evade attention by remaining in a position of complete normality, and which may not be presented as dominant men who subordinate and marginalize other gender expressions.

Methodology

A content analysis was performed taking into consideration the characteristics of hegemonic masculinity identified by Trujillo (1991) such as the way men employ physical force and control over others, the perception of occupational achievement, the participation of familial patriarchy, the sense of frontiersmanship and the exercise of heterosexuality. But also, salient characteristics inherent to the film were recorded and analyzed, such as avoidance of responsibility, the use of the makeover, spatial differentiation, and desirability.

The film's argument

Hitch (2005) is the story of Alex Hitchens, the 'date doctor', who uses statistics and pseudo-science to advise men on how to best approach the women they are secretly infatuated with. But this scientific knowledge masks Hitch's very insecurities product of a bad break up in his youth and that now make him an emotionally guarded man. This guard is put to test when he meets Sara Melas, a successful gossip journalist who is also emotionally distant. They begin a relationship, but complications ensue when Sara's new assignment happens to be Albert Brennaman, Hitch's new client, whose purpose is to win the affection of Allegra Cole, the sole heiress of the Cole fortune.

Physical force and control:

According to Trujillo (1991) physical force and control are characteristics of hegemonic masculinity when dominance through them is shown as men's natural course of action.

This naturalization of physical strength and aggressiveness as an inherent characteristic of male bodies and masculinity is shown throughout the film, in characters such as Albert and Hitch.

Albert is portrayed as a capable accountant possessing an almost uncontrollable strength, and aggressiveness, which are exerted at unexpected moments such as when he tries to clean the coffee he spills over his desk, or when he spills the soda as he tries to clean a mustard drip that fell on his trousers. What appears as mere clumsiness takes a different meaning when frustrated he becomes violent toward himself and the object which surround him, like the umbrella he is unable to close or another mustard drip that fell on his leather jacket (figure 1).

Figure 1. *Hitch* (2005). Frames 0:15:00 / 0:15:44/ 0:44:18 / 1:15:03. Columbia Pictures Corporation.

Albert displays sudden changes between stillness and aggressiveness which are better exemplified when he breaks a bathroom sink as he builds up the courage to be in Allegra's presence (figure 2).

Figura 2. *Hitch* (2005). Frames 0:19:02 / 0:19:04 / 0:19:05. Columbia Pictures Corporation

But his aggressiveness is often directed towards other men, displaying dominance in order to get closer to Allegra as seen when he jumps over his coworkers to give her a pen (figure 3, frame 0:16:52) or when he stands up and yells to his boss to defend Allegra's economic interests. This event helps to differentiate him from the crowd, which wins Allegra's attention but in the tantrum quits his job without realizing it (figure 3, frame 0:22:01)

Figure 3. *Hitch* (2005). Frame 0:16:52 / 0:22:01. Columbia Pictures Corporation.

Nevertheless, his most violent confrontations are reserved to the protection of Allegra from other men, be it when men talk about her sexuality, as occurs when he destroys a newsstand after the newsstand's employee makes fun of her (figure 4, frames 1:12:16 and 1:12:32). Or when he sees Hitch hugging Allegra and violently tries to choke (figure 4, frames 1:39:10 and 1:39:13).

Figure 4. *Hitch* (2005). Frames 1:12:16 / 1:12:32 / 1:39:10 / 1:39:13. Columbia Pictures Corporation.

But regardless of their severity or their unprovoked nature, neither of these aggressive actions carry any consequence against Albert but are seen as part of his inherently protective behavior in line with his masculine nature.

Hitch also uses force throughout the film, be it to restrain Albert's uncontrollable strength as seen when he is getting his body waxed (figure 5, frame 1:13:00) or when he prevents him to appear less manly by crawling back to his boss to get his job back figure 5, frame

Figure 5. *Hitch* (2005). Frames 1:13:00 / 0:23:20. Columbia Pictures Corporation.

And establishes dominance over other men through his command of physical force as seen when he neutralizes Chip by putting a hand on his shoulder and preventing him from making more of his unsolicited advances on Sara, or when he violently reduces Vance by applying an arm lock in a crowded restaurant (figure 6).

Figure 6. *Hitch* (2005). Frames 0:26:37 / 0:31:00. Columbia Pictures Corporation.

The difference from Albert is that Hitch's maintains his serenity while using his physical strength, but like Albert, he loses his temper and can't control himself when Sara is involved in the confrontations, as seen when Sara confronts him for being the secret and infamous 'date doctor', or when he jumps on the roof of Sara's car to desperately ask for a second chance (figure 7).

Figura 1. *Hitch* (2005). Frames 1:24:03 / 1:24:11 / 1:44:42 / 1:44:44. Columbia Pictures Corporation.

These instances naturalize men as the sole bearers of physical force and aggressiveness, which in turn aid to form a hierarchy where those more capable to inflict violence are put at the top while those who are subjugated find a space on the margins of masculinity.

But, while Hitch appears in control of himself, deploying his strength at calculated instances be it to dominate other men, to subdue Albert or to express his frustration, Albert is shown as physically unpredictable and bearing an uncontrollable strength. That is, Albert's body is the representation of brute force, which is masculinized and is eager to respond to any stimulus as

(Komisar 1980) and (Messner 1990) theorize of the use of force by hegemonic men. Albert then incarnates the ideals of a protective man, being defined by others as a “bodyguard” and “shepherd dog”.

And is only after Hitch loses his temper, and behaves more like Albert, that Sara rewards him by giving him a second chance.

Therefore, at the top strata of men capable of exerting force and aggressiveness in a successful manner, we find a division between those who used it in a deliberate and perhaps rational way, like Hitch, and those who are unable to contain it because of their lack of emotional control, such as Albert, which is seen as the more desirable trait in men, and consequently an important characteristic of hegemonic masculinity in the film.

Occupational achievement:

According to (Ochberg 1987), occupational achievement is a trait of hegemonic masculinity when used to define men's state of affairs, that is, when economic activity is defined as 'men's work', which in turns make certain jobs to be more desirable than others.

We observe that the characters in the film are defined by the stereotypes associated with their economic activities.

Hitch is hired as a masculinity counselor for emotionally insecure men, his guidance is always filled with statistics that imbue him with authority, while the other part of his job consists in compiling information about the women his employers wish to court. Hitch's success consists of making men come closer to a normative and more desirable masculinity

In this normative view of masculinity, man as a breadwinner must be capable of assuming dangerous jobs to ensure the survival of those under his command, and in this sense, Hitch's risky but well remunerated job should be at the culprit of the normative ladder, but due to its secrecy, he is bound to live an alienated existence whitening the very structures of patriarchy.

On the other side, Albert works as an accountant in a monotonous corporate environment, undistinguishable from his coworkers up until the time he loses his job for standing against the labor structures and siding up with Allegra Cole.

After this incident Albert doesn't land a new job, so we are let to believe that his savings are invested becoming Allegra's husband with Hitch's help.

At the end of the film, the economic activity of the male protagonist is destroyed while the women, Sara and Allegra, remain in their positions of occupational success.

The men that remain in their position of labor success are Max, Sara's boss, and Vance, the stockbroker reduced by Hitch's strength, and therefore could be seen as in a position of hegemonic masculinity.

Nevertheless, the male protagonists, Albert, and Hitch, cannot wield their economic activities as a potentiator of their masculinity and could be argue that their desirability by women is driven by their lack of concern for their economic stability.

Familial patriarchy:

Familial patriarchy, defined as the male dominance over the family unit, is a trait of hegemonic masculinity when is made to appear as a natural and desirable state of affairs for men (Trujillo, 1991).

In the film, only Sara talks about the importance of her father in her life but is quick to mention his during the traumatic event where her sister almost died in a frozen lake. On the other hand, when she talks about her grandfather, Juan Melas, she regards him as a “horrible family legacy we’ve all tried to forget” since he was involved in war crimes during the Spanish civil war.

Sara has outgrown the biological familial patriarchy by being an independent and successful journalist for a gossip newspaper, but in withing this labor structure her boss, Max, performs as a father figure more concerned about giving her advice on her personal life than on her professional tasks.

Max paternal role can be seen when Sara returns Hitch’s phone call to set up a date, and looks at him for approval (figure 7)

Figure 7. *Hitch* (2005). Frame 0:55:23. Columbia Pictures Corporation.

At the date Hitch is informed that he is to share the table with Sara's boss and his wife, he hesitates in a clear indication that her boss acts as a strong parent figure. The date takes place in a cuisine class, where everybody has to fix their own meal following the chef's instructions, but only the men, Max and Hitch, manipulate the food given to the entire table, while Sara and Louise take on passive roles (figure 8)

Figure 8. *Hitch* (2005). Frames 0:57:17 / 0:57:22 / 0:57:25 / 0:59:17. Columbia Pictures Corporation.

The scene reinforces Max's patriarchal role since he is the first one that to cut and pass the food. When Sara handles the food and feeds it to Hitch, he develops an allergic reaction and has to be treated immediately (figure 9), showing that the act of providing food is safe as long as the patriarch does it, naturalizing men as providers.

Figure 9. *Hitch* (2005). Frames 0:59:01 / 1:00:47. Columbia Pictures Corporation.

Although family relations are subverted in the film, to the extent that Sara reacts in anger when is presented with her grandfather signature at Ellis Island, in the film a sense of familial patriarchy remains as Max substitutes her father figure.

But the male protagonists do not embody any type of familial patriarchy and are not shown as desirable fathers or protectors of a possible family unit.

Frontiersmanship:

Frontiersmanship is a characteristic of hegemonic masculinity when used to define an “ideal man”, that is, a man thought of as ‘natural’ and desirable because of his proclivity to take risks and embody archetypes such as the American cowboy (Kimmel 1987).

In *Hitch* (2005) there are instances where men willingly expose themselves to danger, as when Hitch jumps to the Hudson to save Sara even though he didn’t know how to swim, or when he jumps on top of her car to ask for a second chance.

Beyond the physical plane, and one could argue that most men in the film opt to live a risky existence as soon as they hire the services of the date doctor. This because the men that hire Hitch, are aware that seeking the help of another man to conquer a woman proposes a rupture with normative masculinity.

And while Hitch may have a proclivity to affront physical risks, he is terrified of committing to emotional risks, declaring that opening himself to feelings is the same as “jumping off a plane without a parachute”, which in part is the reason why part of his job is preventing men from getting hurt.

On the other hand, Albert is not afraid of taking emotional risks, to the point of going against Hitch’s advice of letting go of Allegra and calls him a coward.

At the end Hitch acknowledges that Albert is right and decides to go “skydiving” himself, showing that “real men” should not shy away from the greater risk of all which is falling in love.

The film then naturalizes men as natural risk takers, making frontiersmanship a trait of hegemonic masculinity.

Heterosexuality:

According to Connell (1995) one of the important traits of hegemonic masculinity has to do with the fact that men in a position of hegemony regulate the ways in which affection and emotions are displayed, that is, they develop sets of rules for them and the others in order to maintain dominance over society as a whole.

A part of Hitch's job is to regulate the way men display their emotions, making it clear to Albert that he needs to kiss Allegra on their next date to "seal the deal", and confront him with statistics such as how "8 out of 10 women" consider the first kiss as the best way to know how the relationship will evolve, that is, knowing if marriage will occur or not.

Hitch forces Albert to practice the first kiss on him, assuming the role of Allegra by showing effeminate mannerisms (figure 9, frame 0:52:24)

Hitch manages Albert expectations by teaching him how in the ideal kiss the man should approach a 90 percent of the distance, allowing the woman to approach the other 10 percent, and persuades him come closer to him. Albert reluctantly does so, but after Hitch commands him to think of him as the real Allegra, Albert immediately advances 100 percent of the distances and kisses him

Hitch recoils violently and, for the first and only time in the film, he insults Albert by calling him an "overeager son of a (bitch)", nevertheless, Albert is only concerned about how the kiss felt (Figure 9, frames 0:54:33 / 0:54:34).

Figure 9. *Hitch* (2005). Frames 0:52:24 / 0:54:33 / 0:54:34. Columbia Pictures Corporation.

Here Albert is penalized because of his transgression, which reflects the marginalization of men that challenge the normative heterosexuality by conducting homosexual acts but not so much when performing as effeminate, as Hitch does. This presents heterosexuality as a natural and desirable practice for men and an important characteristic of hegemonic masculinity,

Along with the hegemonic masculinity traits identified by Trujillo (1991), other distinguishing characteristics emerged from the film, such as: the avoidance of responsibility, the use of the makeover, racial relations, Male gaze deployment and spatial differentiation, and desirability

Avoidance of responsibility:

Hitch is never shown as a serial stalker, willing to spy on anyone in order to 'help' men, on the contrary, he is presented as product of a cruel past, a victim of unrequited love and the protector of the few 'good' men out there.

The same happens with Albert, and the rest of Hitch's employers, who are shown as victims of their own awkwardness, incapable of pursuing a relationship with women, but the reality is that they are men willing to hire "the date doctor" to spy on women they have idealized.

These men are shielded from major criticism throughout the film, and are shown under a sympathetic light, naturalizing the sense that they are not to be held accountable in their pursuit of love, or as Hitch puts it "I'm a man, since when do we get things right the first time?"

Therefore, in the film the avoidance of responsibility is a trait of hegemonic masculinity, as it allows for morally dubious men to emerge as heroic figures, whose actions are motivated by external forces and not by their own volition.

Use of the makeover:

Throughout the film the makeover serves as a tool to reroute male anxieties over their looks into a more “normal” way to present themselves.

When Albert expresses his apprehension about his weight, Hitch advise him to shave his back and change his wardrobe from suits to leather jackets (Figure 10, frames 0:15:21 / 1:15:11). Which stems from Hitch’s own experience with the makeover, as he has gone from awkward teenager to the sharp “date doctor” (Figure 10, frames 0:12:49 / 0:15:13)

Figure 10. *Hitch* (2005). Frames 0:15:21 / 1:15:11 / 0:12:49 / 0:15:13. Columbia Pictures Corporation.

This makeover doesn’t imbue masculinity in men but aims to make their masculinity more visible by forcing them into normalcy, as seen when Hitch forces Neil to wear shoes he doesn’t like, and when he forces Albert to wax his back. The makeover in the film makes men look

normal and desirable by molding them under the patriarchal aesthetic code of success and rebelliousness exemplified by Hitch's suit and Albert's jacket respectively.

Spatial differentiation

Throughout the film men are placed next to the women they desire as seen in the way Albert is always closer to Allegra (figure 11, frame 0:24:03) or the way Hitch is closer to Sara (figure 11, frame 0:37:10). When this fails to happen both, Hitch and Albert, act aggressively be it by jumping over coworkers in the case of Albert or dominating other men in the case of Hitch.

Figure 11. *Hitch* (2005). Frames 0:24:03 / 0:37:10. Columbia Pictures Corporation.

Also, men in a position of hegemony are shown as taller and bigger than the rest of the characters on the screens, such is the case when Max appears next to Sara and Geoff. And the same happens when Hitch speaks with an Albert that begs for his services (figure 12)

Figura 2. *Hitch* (2005). Frames 0:08:00 / 0:08:14 / 0:16:05. Columbia Pictures Corporation.

Nevertheless, this pattern is disrupted when Hitch kisses Sara for the first time, and she is shown almost as tall as him, which doesn't reflect their real heights as seen in frame (figure 13).

Figure 13. *Hitch* (2005). Frames 0:37:55 / 1:08:30. Columbia Pictures Corporation.

This change in height might have to do with the fact that in their first kiss Sara is the one who approaches Hitch, breaking the rule of women only coming 10 percent of the distance on their first kiss. But it is after the breaking of this rule that they begin experiencing difficulties and end breaking up. It is only when they are both shown at their real height and when Hitch approaches 90 percent of the distance to kiss her that we are led to believe they lived happily ever after (figure 14)

Figure 14. Hitch (2005). Frames 1:46:07. Columbia Pictures Corporation.

The spatial differentiation between the characters in the film reinforces the idea that men should appear bigger, dominant, and closer to the women they desire, therefore making a dominant physical presence an important characteristic of hegemonic masculinity.

Desirability

In the rom-com men are thought of as successful when they win the hearts of the women they desire. Therefore, the women are in a position to validate the different manifestations of masculinity presented by each male character in the film.

Special attention was taken on the way women described men, that is, in the adjectives they used to describe them. Only Hitch, Albert, Vance, Max, and Juan Melas, were described by women, of these only Hitch, Albert and Vance were described as possible love interest in the film diegesis. The word clouds of adjectives used by women to describe these men are shown in figure 15 as shown as follows in the tag clouds obtained through NVivo 11.

Figure 15. Adjectives used by women to male characters in *Hitch* (2005)

From these word clouds we can see that Albert is described in the most favorable way, above Hitch and Vance, and therefore seen as the one that better incarnates masculinity's hegemonic ideals. This is reinforced by the end of the film when Hitch appropriates Albert's behavior in the pursuit of Sara, since his persona as the 'date doctor' has proven to be incompatible with what women look for in a man.

At the end of the film, Hitch's normativity, displayed as 'basic principles', is portrayed as a straitjacket that doesn't allow him to become the ideal man women recognize in Albert. But if Hitch exemplifies a masculinity that needs to be created, Albert exemplifies a masculinity rooted in a male essence, which is seen as natural, of common sense and desirable.

Conclusion

In *Hitch* (2005), the deployment of aggressive behavior and physical force are shown as inherent characteristics of hegemonic masculinity by presenting them as desirable traits in men, such as Albert and Hitch, who are recognized as embodying an ideal masculinity, and are believed to be entitled to a romantic relationship with women, only after they make use of the physical force contained in them. And even when the use of physical force is not exclusive of men, in the film the idea of male bodies possessing greater capabilities for violence and aggressiveness is normalized.

Hegemonic masculinity in the film is also defined by men's ability to take risks, such as Hitch's employers who aware of the social consequences for public ridicule if caught, still go ahead, and use his hitch's services, therefore integrating the frontiersman ideal to their persona.

Other men, like Hitch and Albert, assume deeper risks because to gain access to their desired women they have to quit their professional careers, which helped to define them as thriving men. This puts forth the idea that a successful relationship between men and women must be mediated by male sacrifice and female compliance.

The film also shows the relationship between men as safe and fructiferous, as long as the men are in the same social strata, but they must remain vigilant of not being effeminate, soft, or homosexual, always willing to respond with physical force if their heterosexuality is challenged.

Also, in the film, hegemonic masculinity is tied to the ideals of familial patriarchy, having men act as protectors and providers. Naturalizing the perpetuation of patriarchal structures as men

regard themselves as bearers of an unquestionable male essence; by which “men will always be men” regardless of culture, geography, or time period.

This idea of a male essence is exploited through the makeover, which is used to shed the layers of softness from the primal, and more desirable, male underneath.

Furthermore, the male gaze throughout the film is almost permanent, guiding the audience to see women, and ‘soft’ men, as objects to be look-at, or to be possessed.

In *Hitch* (2005), the men that access a hegemonic position are those intrinsically aggressive, or at least capable to dominate women and other men. They are willing to take risks while remaining loyal to the patriarchal structures they draw benefits from. They are vigilant of their heterosexuality and are always ready to avoid any responsibility by blaming their actions on a male essence that lies beyond any social construct of gender.

Hitch (2005) presents itself as a film about a man coming to the realization that there are no rules in the romantic arena, but what this research has found is that to be successful, men need to pay close attention to the ‘basic principles’ hidden in a game of male fantasy and hegemonic masculinity.

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